

**THE ROLE AND FUNCTIONS OF THE INTELLECTUAL SYSTEM OF
LEARNING IN THE ELECTRONIC INFORMATION-EDUCATIONAL
ENVIRONMENT**

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The modern stage of society's development is characterized by economic and social reforms aimed at deep penetration of scientific and technical achievements into all spheres of human activity. This puts high demands on the scientific and cultural ethics, professional skills, creativity, and the qualities of science and technology. The science of pedagogy plays an important role in solving these problems in the higher education system.

"Global financial and economic crisis, elimination in the conditions of Uzbekistan." ways and measures'? In his work, the main causes of the crisis were analyzed and a set of measures was determined to eliminate its consequences. One of the main tasks of modernization is the wide introduction of modern technologies to various sectors of the economy and social sphere, including the education system.

Education system cannot be developed without widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies. In this regard, the modern higher education system promotes the use of information and communication technologies as an important tool for the professional activity of future specialists. Several positive experiences have been collected in the republic regarding the use of information and communication technologies. At the same time, the analysis of the activities of specialists who are engaged in practical work shows that there is a

need to thoroughly prepare graduates of non-specialist bachelor's education to use information technologies in their professional activities.

In modern conditions, the main demand for the education system is for the learner. His interests, needs, abilities, motivations should be taken into more consideration when designing teaching and independent work processes. The modern state of the organization of study processes is characterized by a number of features:

- rational selection of educational content, taking into account individual needs and individual characteristics, development of criteria, methods and principles in this regard;

- the standardization of organizational form and teaching methods, as well as the need to organize pedagogical processes in the case of individualization of education;

- researching ways of designing teaching systems aimed at improving students' independent work in developing solutions to problems in this regard;

- development of integration of pedagogy and information technologies for the individual, which increases the relevance of developing the pedagogical foundations of the design of intellectual systems.

Thus, in the organization of educational processes, students have the tasks of developing their professional and creative abilities related to the ability to analyze the possibilities of various intellectual systems, to try new ways of using them in specific fields of science in solving educational problems.

The widespread introduction of information and communication technologies is considered one of the global trends in the development of modern techniques and technologies. The rapid development of informatization in our country creates opportunities for creating new software products for the educational sector. At the same time, despite the fact that information and communication technologies are developing at a high pace, the scientific

justification of the development and introduction of intellectual systems, new methods, forms and means of organizing students' independent work is not satisfactory.

In such conditions, the demand for specialists who have mastered the fundamentals of sciences, pedagogy and psychology methods, have high professional qualities, and can use information and communication technologies in practice is increasing. At the same time, the implementation of the principles of personalized education leads to an increase in the burden on each trained pedagogue. This causes problems related to the effective distribution of pedagogues' time in the organization of the learning process in educational institutions, in turn, this problem causes the need to identify the technology, form and teaching methods aimed at reducing the level of workload of pedagogues, and at the same time to meet the requirements of education adapted to the individual.

The content of theoretical sources, the analysis of the experience of organizing the learning process in higher education institutions showed that the development of intellectual systems is one of the most optimal forms of introducing modern information technologies to the organization of students' independent work.

The problems of using modern educational tools and the approaches to their solution are reflected in the works of our country and foreign scientists on psychology, pedagogy and computer science. The principles of training future specialists in the field of information and educational technologies have been developed in the theory and practice of higher education. A. A. Abdukodirov, L. I. Antsiferov, V. M. Vymyatin, A. Ya. Vagramenko, E. P. Velikhov, V. M. Glushkov, F. M. Zakirova, M. Z. The works of Ziyahodzhaev, V.A. Izvozchikov, M.P. Lapchik, V.M. Monakhov and others are particularly important.

Talim zharayonida yangi akhborot technologylaridan foidalanish masalalari A.A.Abdukodirov, A.H.Abdullaev, N.V.Apatov, M.Aripov, B.Begalov,

V.P.Bespalko, P.L.Galperin, B.S.Gershunsky , E. I. Zueva, M. V. Lapchik, A. R. Marakhimov, E. I. Mashbits, N. A. Muslimov, I. V. Robert, G. K. Selevko, N. I. Taylakov, N. F. .Talizina, R.H.Khamdamov, U.Yuldoshevlarning ishlarida uz aksini topgan.

We understand the informatization of education as a process aimed at improving the quality of education, organizing research, replacing traditional information technology systems with more effective ones in all types of educational activities, implementing, developing and simultaneously monitoring.

New information technologies help students to develop such qualities as systematic scientific thinking, constructive thinking, developed imagination, developed intuition, spatial and associative thinking, and the ability to perceive novelty.

In order to increase the efficiency and quality of the learning process, the tasks of providing psychological-pedagogical and methodical developments aimed at identifying the most acceptable conditions for the use of information technologies are of great importance. The relevance of the situations listed above is determined not only by the social order, but also by the needs of the individual to determine his position and express his opinion:

It follows from this that the problem of designing an intellectual system of education and its implementation is considered an urgent problem of our time. The creation of this system is related to the planning and implementation of the educational process, which takes into account the educational goals. In accordance with this, it is possible to distinguish the stages of pedagogical planning: setting goals and clarifying them as much as possible; organization of the Ukuv process based on the preparation of Ukuv materials in accordance with Ukuv purposes; evaluating the current results, adapting to the educational process aimed at achieving the set goals; final evaluation of results.

The implementation of these steps is carried out according to the algorithms applied to the intellectual system of learning:

- 1) description of the ultimate goals of educational processes;
- 2) description of intermediate goals by diagnostic indicators;
- 3) designing educational content in a reasonable way;
- 4) to recommend standard educational technologies provided with methods that guarantee the achievement of the set goals and objectively control the quality of education;
- 5) description of educational conditions and organizational forms. The use of information technologies for educational purposes requires a thorough study and assessment of the potential impact of these technologies on educational content and methods.

Such studies should focus not only on the impact of information technologies on educational methods, but also on the didactic levels of information technology design and implementation.

We learned the content of the principles implemented during the didactic process. These principles determine the system of requirements for both traditional and computer technologies.

These include the following:

- compliance of didactic process and didactic system with educational requirements;
- the leading role of theoretical education;
- unity of educational, educational and developmental tasks;
- encouraging students' positive attitudes towards education;
- difficulty; to carry out teamwork in education with an individual approach;
- to combine abstract thinking with visualization;
- orientation of education to personal activity;

- the compatibility of educational information base with educational content and didactic system.

The intellectual system of education, based on comprehensive activation of students' cognitive activity, can be effective only if the psychophysiological and psychological characteristics of students are taken into account, and if there is a system that diagnoses and corrects the qualities of a person that are important for education and professional activity. Using the intellectual system of education is considered one of the factors of development and individualization of personal activity, motivational and personal management of this activity. It is possible to achieve success as a result of using the intellectual system of education only when there is an active search that comes from the existing motivational field, which is achieved through the formation of a plan of actions. At the current stage of the development of computer education in higher education institutions, the following are the reasons for developing the intellectual system of education: higher efficiency of work, its organization, activity, quality of learning, independence, availability of fair assessment, discipline.

It is necessary and important for the student to always develop according to the needs of the times.

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